

Role of School Social Worker in Psychosocial Issues with Children and Adolescents

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Abstract- Aggression, low self-esteem, anxiety, depression, and anger are typical in school-age children and adolescents. These issues are a sign of mental health disorders and psychosocial problems. With 34.8% of the population between the ages of 0 and 19 in 2021, India has the highest percentage of children and adolescents globally. A WHO report states that 10–20% of all children suffer from one or more mental or behavioral issues. Parents spend their wealth beyond their means to support their children's education and demands because they want them to do well in school. However, parents lack the time to deal with hidden problems in their children's lives that affect their behavior, health, social skills, and academic performance. In raising children, all parties involved—parents, educators, and the community—are accountable, but the hidden problems that affect well-being and academic performance are not addressed. If proper care and attention are not provided during this transitional period, adolescents are at risk of developing several psychosocial issues that will affect their cognitive abilities, academic stress, problem-solving skills, depression symptoms, and general mental health for a long time. Programs for school-based support are crucial for recognizing and resolving these issues early. School social workers possess both theoretical understanding and practical experience at the levels of individuals, families, schools, and communities. This study explains the psychological problems and how they affect the lives of students. The results show that a person's emotional, behavioral, cognitive, and social aspects are influenced by a variety of socioeconomic, environmental, technological, social, and relationship factors. Thus, school social workers can provide coping mechanisms in a variety of ways.

Keywords- Psychosocial Issues, School Social Worker, Intervention, Impact of Issues.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every parent aspires to support their children's decisions and strive to give them more than their financial means and constraints allow. Their hectic schedules and financial struggles prevent them from paying attention to their children's hidden problems, which impede their development, academic performance, and tranquility. According to

research, a person's character is shaped by their early experiences, affection, fear, sexual abuse, parental love, and their environment. These elements manifest during adolescence, when children are going through hormonal changes and developing the ability to visualize things. Many issues pertaining to emotions and behaviors start or exacerbate during adolescence. Adolescents and children in school are going through a difficult time preparing to handle social interactions, identity,

motivation, and goal confusion, adjustment difficulties, and conflict as they work toward independence from their parents while still requiring their guidance and support. Their behavioral and emotional development may be impacted by the biological, psychological, and social changes that occur during adolescence (Mumthas & Muhsina, 2014; Nimje et al., 2023). When mental, emotional, social, and behavioral problems come together and impact people's thoughts, feelings, actions, and social interactions, they become psychosocial problems. These issues are fleeting and frequently difficult to identify. To gain a profound understanding of psychosocial issues, break them down. "Psycho" refers to mental and emotional aspects (thoughts, emotions, personality, mental health, coping mechanisms), while "social" refers to environmental and relational aspects (peer relationships, family dynamics, cultural and community context, economic conditions, education, and employment). When there is a disruption in the family, economic, social, and emotional spheres, children experience anxiety and depression and begin projecting their feelings of loneliness, anger, and depression into substance abuse, suicide, depression medications, and unethical behavior. The term psychosocial encompasses both internalizing and externalizing issues; delinquency, aggression, conduct disorder, hyperactivity, academic difficulties, suicidality, and truancy are examples of externalizing issues, while depression and anxiety are examples of internalizing issues (Bista, 2016; Bhosale et al., 2015; Nimje et al., 2023). Nowadays, most families or couples live in unitary arrangements and work due to urbanization and rapid industrialization; consequently, they inevitably have less time to care for their children. These conditions are contributing to an increase in psychiatric and psychosocial (behavioral and emotional) issues (Ahmad et al., 2007; Nimje et al., 2023). The stage of life that comes after childhood but before adulthood is called adolescence (Banstola, 2017; Yadav, 2021). Behavioral and emotional issues affect children's health and well-being, and children's behavior is a reflection of their mental health (Ray, 2022). The development of mental health issues is influenced by expectations about education, career success,

gender discrimination, anxiety, interpersonal conflicts, strained relationships, and dysfunctional family dynamics (Ray, 2022).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A community-based descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Maharashtra's urban field with 330 adolescents, of whom 214 actively participated (Nimje et al., 2023). The results of the PSC-Y indicated that a significant portion of the adolescents (roughly one-third) had psychosocial issues and required assistance with interventions. Using SDQ, Masare et al. (2019) carried out a cross-sectional study to find out how parents and teachers perceived psychosocial problems in their kids. According to the findings, parents, caregivers, educators, and medical professionals should be aware of the signs of mental health issues in their children. Balamurugan et al. (2024) systematically reviewed thirty studies. A wide variety of mental health issues with varying degrees of severity and frequency have been reported in school-age children and adolescents. According to the analysis, the most common mental health condition among children was depression, which was followed by attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, social, behavioral, and emotional issues, anxiety, psychological distress, internet technology addiction, stress, social phobia, violence, and sexual and emotional abuse. According to the study's findings, researching school mental health in India is essential for tailoring interventions to the unique needs of the varied student body, reducing stigma, and improving general student wellbeing within the nation's cultural and educational framework. Yadav (2021) looks at the importance of different psychological concepts and psychosocial problems. Teenagers are particularly vulnerable during this time and require extra care because they deal with peer relationships, academic pressure, substance abuse, and health adjustment issues. According to Harikrishnan & Salio (2021), school-age adolescents faced a variety of challenges during their life stages, and fewer parents were counseling their children privately. According to the qualitative findings, parents and school-age adolescents knew a little bit about school counselors or social workers. Strong

capacity building, school-community collaboration, and long-term plans and programs are all important components of school social work practice. According to Meenu's (2010) research, schools do not have social workers or counselors on staff, nor do they have training programs for teachers and parents. The study discovered that while social workers were providing counseling and follow-up, they were providing more counseling in private schools, and fewer schoolchildren were talking to social workers about their problems.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the psychosocial issues and their impact on school-going children and adolescents.
- To assess the school social work practice in psychosocial issues.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The prevalence of psychosocial problems in children and adolescents is evaluated and described in this study. School social workers can identify and address psychosocial issues early on using a variety of theoretical and practical approaches. The descriptive nature of the current study is supported by extensive reports, literature, websites, and other sources.

Psychosocial Issues With Children And Adolescents

Psychosocial issues encompass a broad spectrum of mental health conditions that affect students' emotional states, behavior, and cognitive processes. (Gull et al, 2025). India has the highest percentage of children and adolescents in the world; in 2021, 34.8% of the population was between the ages of 0 and 19 (Balamurgan et al., 2024). According to a WHO report, 10–20% of children have one or more behavioral or mental health issues (WHO, 2021; Vijayender Goud et al., 2025). While some students are fortunate enough to have parental support when they struggle with anxiety, depression, peer

pressure, poor academic performance, and low self-esteem, others do not receive any support at all and experience psychological issues. In certain situations, the stigma attached to mental health issues in families can result in a lack of support and understanding, which makes it even more difficult for the person to get help. According to a UNICEF survey from early 2021, only 41% of Indian youths aged 15 to 24 said that getting help for mental health issues is beneficial, indicating that children in the country were reluctant to seek help for mental stress (Balamurugan, 2024; UNICEF, 2021). This study concentrates on psychosocial problems and the methods used by school social workers to detect them early.

Internalizing Issues	Externalizing Issues	Outcomes of Psychosocial Issues
Anxiety, depression	Poverty, neglect	Low self-esteem, school dropout
Trauma, abuse	Bullying, discrimination	Aggression, isolation
Identity confusion	Peer pressure	Risky behaviors, eating disorders
Grief, Loss	Lack of Support System	Substance abuse, self-harm

A state of worry or fear is called anxiety. Students face many issues when they are suddenly faced with unfamiliar situations, such as parental relocation, migration, social settings, peer conflict, and academic performance (Gull et al., 2024). Children feel stressed and depressed when they are under pressure to perform well academically and fulfill their academic responsibilities. Distress is linked to eating disorders, anxiety, depression, and a rise in the use of drugs to feel happy right away, while ignoring the issues. According to a study by Gore & Morgan (2024), several things, including subpar work, low grades, assignments, tests, exam patterns, and tardiness in class, can cause this stress. According to Gore and Morgan (2024), adolescents often experience identity confusion and engage in time-wasting and illegal activities, such as stealing and unethical money-making. Children and teenagers deal with a variety of issues in their academic lives, including psychological stress, academic stress, anxiety, depression, suicidal thoughts, emotional and behavioral issues, and drug addiction. Graph 1 illustrates the emotional and behavioral problems, family and relationship problems, school difficulties, financial difficulties, and academic obstacles that are prevalent psychosocial problems and affect various facets of

children's academic development and general well-being. Gore & Morgan (2024) stress the importance of interpersonal and communication skills, and that professionals must collaborate closely with parents and other caregivers of children and adolescents.

IMPACT OF PSYCHOSOCIAL ISSUES:

- impacts prosocial behavior, mental health, conduct, emotions, and thought patterns.
- Academic distractions, goal-setting, and performance
- ruin relationships with family, friends, peers, teachers, and siblings.
- Prolonged psychological problems can result in health problems, headaches, chest pain, musculoskeletal pain, chronic fatigue, weakness, acidity, eating disorders, and digestive issues.

Factors Of Psychosocial Issues

Socioeconomic factors

A person's mental health is influenced by both personal characteristics and societal circumstances. Adolescents who lack socioeconomic independence during this period of transition from childhood to adulthood frequently experience a number of crises and problems; inadequate care and attention increases the risk of developing a variety of psychosocial issues that could have a lasting effect (Sharma et al., 2014) and significantly affect their psychosocial adjustment and academic performance in school (Haynes, 2002). According to Ray (2022) and Balamurgan (2024), parents' low educational attainment and poverty are major

contributors to their children's developing psychosocial problems.

Environmental Factors

According to Bronfenbrenner (1997), ecological system theory generalizes the Microsystem, Mesosystem, Macrosystem, Exosystem, and Chronosystem; however, the surrounding environment is common in all systems, indicating that the environment plays a significant role in the formation of character, confidence, and behavior. Peer groups, family environments, violence, abuse, discrimination, academic support, beliefs about doing, sports, and the ability to choose one's dreams, among other things, are factors that shape children's perceptions, both positive and negative, during the childhood to adolescent stage. Adolescents and children who experience bullying, violence, discrimination, excessive academic pressure, or abuse without the support of their parents or teachers grow depressed and, regrettably, occasionally attempt suicide because they lack coping mechanisms.

Social and Relationship Factors

Children experience emotional outbursts and behavioral changes when they have a strong attachment to someone and have experienced tragedy, grief, or loss. These types of relationship tragedies affect children's education and general well-being. Social stigma associated with caste, color, disability, poor academic performance, languages, and the social environment has an impact on children's mental health and academic performance. Since people may be afraid of being judged, rejected, or facing unfavorable outcomes, this stigma makes it difficult for them to ask for assistance and support. Individuals may thus put off or refrain from seeking treatment, which could lead to subpar or postponed care and worsen their condition.

The Impact of Technology

Every child has access to smartphones, social media accounts, YouTube, and other platforms where they can engage in entertainment activities such as watching vulgar content, thinking about modernity,

and fashion. In addition to creating their own identities, adolescents take pleasure in gaining more social media followers. Children became overly dependent on smartphones after COVID-19, and even schools now encourage students to use their phones for homework, research, and study materials. India has made mental health and sustainable development goals a priority. Target 3.4 is to "promote mental health and well-being and reduce by one-third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment by 2030 (Ray, 2022). It is now necessary to concentrate on the concerning state of mental health in India following the COVID-19 pandemic to accomplish such goals (Ray, 2022).

School Social Worker In The Context Of Psychosocial Issues

India began practicing school social work in the 1970s, and TISS, the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, was a pioneer in this field (Meenu, 2010; Harikrishnan & Sailo, 2021). The profession of social work includes promoting social justice, social change, and the dignity and empowerment of individuals and groups in society (Australian Association of Social Work [AASW], 2014; Ioannou et al., 2023). The expansion of services beyond casework was highlighted by Allen-Meares (1990), and group therapy was another social work approach brought to schools. Meenu (2010), Lakshmi (2014), Harikrishnan & Sailo (2021), and Vetter et al. (2024) illustrated the promotion of social work practice in schools using techniques and intervention strategies. However, India lacks school-based mental health services, which can affect children's chances of achieving their full potential and overall well-being (Gore & Morgan, 2024; Kumar, 2021). To create a non-stigmatized environment that supports these students' academic and personal development, all school-based policies should prioritize inclusivity and make the required accommodations to support their special learning needs.

Given that both the parent and the child may be dealing with emotional and behavioral problems,

educational staff members need to be sensitive to parental concerns and treat parents and their children with dignity and respect. which frequently affects both parents' and children's self-esteem. It is more probable that children with emotional and behavioral disorders will perform poorly in school and be less likely to participate in extracurricular social activities (Masare et al., 2019).

School social workers are particularly skilled at connecting with students during their fieldwork practices and comprehending family and community systems. To address the hidden issues of students, they should engage with cultural diversity, systems theory, social justice, risk assessment and intervention, consultation and collaboration, and clinical intervention techniques during their training period (Lakshmi, 2014). School social workers create and carry out school-based initiatives to foster a supportive learning environment for all students. When more intensive interventions with students and the community are required, school social workers can use the Multi-Tiered System of Support (MTSS) throughout the entire school to determine the needs of each student (Vetter, 2021).

School social workers can offer guidance and training on identifying students with mental health needs and how to refer them when services are sought. They are a resource to the principal, teachers, parents, and special educators. collaborating more closely with each student and their family. A school social worker can coordinate various strategies among students, schools, the community, and families. In order to address psychosocial issues, school social workers are qualified to employ both primary and secondary methods. Identification of the signs of behavioral, emotional, social, hyperactive, and peer relationship issues is crucial for early intervention. Social research enables school social workers to use casework, group work, and community organization techniques to implement CBT (Cognitive Behavioral Therapy), group therapy, and BMT (Behavioral Modification Therapy) to improve the family

environment and lessen disruptions (Agarwal & Gairola, 2024).

The person's deteriorating functioning signals a change in family responsibilities and creates stress for the entire family unit. The school social worker can help both high-risk and low-risk students with psychosocial problems by using response to intervention and evidence-based practice.

IV. CONCLUSION

Students with psychosocial problems frequently experience behavioral, emotional, social, or academic challenges that can hinder their growth and academic achievement. Early detection and resolution of these issues depend on the implementation of successful psychosocial interventions, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, individual and group counseling, and school-based support programs. To implement these interventions, school social workers are essential because they foster positive school climates, connect families, schools, and communities, and offer at-risk students focused support. Their efforts enhance students' academic performance and general well-being by lowering mental health symptoms, strengthening coping mechanisms, and promoting resilience. School social workers are trained to understand family and community systems and use these skills to help students in the field. They are trained in risk assessment, social justice, cultural diversity, systems theory, and intervention techniques to deal with students' hidden issues.

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